

Exploring the Temperature Dependent Magnetic Properties and Magnetoimpedance Effect in Fe-rich Microwires for Temperature Monitoring

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Abstract—In this work, we provide new experimental results on temperature dependence of hysteresis loops and the Giant MagnetoImpedance (GMI) effect of amorphous $\text{Fe}_{75}\text{B}_9\text{Si}_{12}\text{C}_4$ microwires. We observed a remarkable improvement of GMI ratio and modification of hysteresis loops from rectangular to inclined upon heating. The observed experimental results are discussed considering relaxation of internal stresses upon heating, Hopkinson effect and modification of the thermal expansion coefficients upon heating.

Keywords- *Magnetic microwires; Magnetic softness; Giant magnetoimpedance effect; Internal stresses; Magnetic anisotropy.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Amorphous magnetic materials are commonly considered among the most promising magnetic materials because of their excellent magnetic and mechanical properties [1]-[5]. Such amorphous materials can be prepared with planar (ribbons) or cylindrical (wires) shapes.

Magnetic wires can have unique magnetic properties, such as magnetic bistability [6]-[8] and/or giant magnetoimpedance, GMI, effect [9]-[11], which are suitable for development of several technological applications [12]-[15]. Therefore, research on amorphous magnetic wires has attracted substantial attention since the 70-s [6]-[15].

Recently, substantial attention has been paid to development of amorphous materials with new functionalities, such as reduced dimensions, enhanced corrosion resistance or biocompatibility [11][13]. Therefore, great attention has been paid to development of alternative fabrication methods allowing preparation of biocompatible amorphous materials with reduced dimensionality [11][13].

Accordingly, studies of glass-coated microwires with reduced diameters (between 0.5 and 100 μm), covered with thin, insulating, biocompatible and flexible glass-coating prepared by the Taylor-Ulitovsky method have attracted great attention [11] [13]. Such microwires are covered with thin, insulating, biocompatible and flexible glass-coating allowing better corrosion resistance and biocompatibility. Additionally, such microwire can present excellent magnetic softness or magnetic bistability [11] [13]. Such features of glass-coated microwires allow development of new exciting applications in various magnetic sensors, as well as in smart composites with tunable magnetic permittivity [6][11][13]-[21]. One more advantage of glass-coated microwires is their excellent mechanical properties [4] [5].

One of the most promising applications of glass-coated microwires is the external stimuli (temperature, stress, magnetic field) monitoring [22]-[25]. As was previously demonstrated [22], the dispersion of the effective permittivity, ϵ_{ef} , of the composites with magnetic wire inclusions depends on the metallic wires geometry, as well as on the magnetic wires impedance. The utilization of ferromagnetic wires allows tuning of this dispersion through changing the wire magnetic structure by external stimuli (magnetic field, stress or temperature) [22]-[25].

For such applications, studies of temperature dependence of the GMI effect are essentially relevant. However, there are only very few studies on temperature dependence of GMI and most studies were performed in different amorphous materials (ribbons or thick magnetic wires without glass-coating) [26]-[29].

In this paper, we provide our recent experimental results on temperature dependence of the GMI effect and hysteresis loops for Fe-rich ($\text{Fe}_{75}\text{B}_9\text{Si}_{12}\text{C}_4$) microwires.

This paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the experimental methods, as well as the microwires characteristics analyzed in this paper are provided. Section 3 presents the experimental results dealing with temperature dependence of hysteresis loops and GMI effect. Finally, we conclude the paper in Section 4.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SYSTEM DETAILS

Amorphous $\text{Fe}_{75}\text{B}_9\text{Si}_{12}\text{C}_4$ glass-coated microwires (metallic nucleus diameter, $d=15.2\ \mu\text{m}$, total diameter, $D=17.2\ \mu\text{m}$) with positive magnetostriction coefficient, λ_s , ($\lambda_s \approx 38 \times 10^{-6}$), have been prepared using the Taylor-Ulitovsky method, previously described elsewhere [16] [18].

The hysteresis loops have been measured using MicroSense EV9 Vibration Sample Magnetometer (VSM), as well as using fluxmetric methods. The latter was previously successfully employed for characterization of magnetically soft microwires at room temperature [30], while utilization of VSM magnetometry allowed to measure the hysteresis loops of 5 mm long samples from room temperature up to 300 °C, as described elsewhere [31]. The hysteresis loops were represented as the dependence of normalized magnetization, M/M_0 (where M is the magnetic moment at a given magnetic field and M_0 is the magnetic moment of the sample at the maximum magnetic field amplitude measured at room temperature) versus magnetic field, H .

Specially designed experimental set-up allows to measure sample impedance and evaluate $\Delta Z/Z$ -ratio in the temperature, T , range from room up to $T=300\ \text{°C}$ at frequencies, f , up to 110 MHz [32].

We used the GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z$, determined as:

$$\Delta Z/Z = [Z(H) - Z(H_{max})] / Z(H_{max}), \quad (1)$$

where Z is impedance of the wire, H and H_{max} are the applied and maximum DC magnetic fields.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As shown in Figure 1, a rectangular hysteresis loop is observed for as-prepared $\text{Fe}_{75}\text{B}_9\text{Si}_{12}\text{C}_4$ glass-coated microwire, as expected for Fe-rich microwire with positive λ_s [18].

A remarkable change in hysteresis loop is observed upon heating: the hysteresis loops of studied sample becomes essentially non-rectangular (see Figure 2a). The substantial effect of heating can be better appreciated from Figure 2b, where the change in the low field hysteresis loop upon heating is shown. Rectangular hysteresis loop transforms into inclined upon heating (see Figure 2b).

The observed changes in hysteresis loops upon heating are almost completely reversible: as shown in Figure 3, the

Figure 1. Hysteresis loops of as-prepared sample.

hysteresis loop measured after heating up to 300 °C and cooling back to room temperature becomes again rectangular.

The aforementioned GMI effect is successfully explained in terms of skin effect of magnetically soft conductors. The origin of the GMI effect is related to the effect of a magnetic field, H , on the penetration depth, δ , of an electrical current flowing through the magnetically soft conductor [9]-[11]. The relationship between δ and the circumferential magnetic permeability, μ_ϕ , for the case of magnetic wires is given by:

Figure 2. Hysteresis loops of studied sample, measured at different T . (a). Low field hysteresis loops (b) measured at the same T .

Figure 3. Hysteresis loops of studied sample, measured before and after heating up to 300 °C.

$$\delta = \sqrt{\pi\sigma\mu_\phi f} \quad (2)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity and f the frequency of the current along the sample.

Accordingly, high $\Delta Z/Z$ -ratio values are usually observed in magnetic wires with high μ_ϕ - values, typically observed in amorphous wires with low transversal magnetic anisotropy [9]-[11][23].

As reported elsewhere [11], for magnetic wires with rectangular hysteresis loops, the $\Delta Z/Z$ -ratio values are usually rather low. However, the observed influence of heating on the shape of the hysteresis loops suggests a modification of the GMI effect. Figure 4 shows the results of the temperature dependence of the GMI effect of studied microwire. Indeed, evidenced from Figure 4, a remarkable increase in $\Delta Z/Z$ -ratio is observed for the studied sample upon heating (see Figure 4). Temperature dependencies of maximum GMI ratio, $\Delta Z/Z_{max}$, for 50 and 100 MHz are summarized in Figure 4c.

The origin of the rectangular hysteresis loop of Fe-rich microwires is commonly attributed to the peculiar domain structure of as-prepared Fe-rich microwires consisting of axially magnetized inner single domain and outer domain shell with radial magnetization [6] [7] [33]. Axial magnetic anisotropy of as-prepared Fe-rich microwires ($\lambda_s > 0$) is commonly explained considering preferentially axial character of the internal stresses arising during the fabrication process consisting of simultaneous rapid solidification of metallic nucleus surrounded by glass-coating with rather different thermal expansion coefficients [18] [34] [35]. The main origin of such stresses is the difference in thermal expansion coefficients of the glass-coating and the metallic nucleus. Accordingly, the heating effect on hysteresis loops shape must be attributed to a decrease in internal stresses upon heating.

Figure 4. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies of studied sample measured at 50 (a) and 100 MHz (b) at various temperatures and $\Delta Z/Z_{max}(T)$ dependencies evaluated for 50 and 100 MHz (c).

The transformation of the hysteresis loops from rectangular to inclined must be the main reason of remarkable GMI effect improvement.

Upon samples heating, several processes are expected: the reduction of internal stresses originated by the rapid solidification of a composite microwire with a different thermal expansion coefficient of the metal nucleus and glass coating and relaxation of internal stresses (as in any amorphous materials). Additionally, the origin of the substantial GMI effect improvement at $T=300$ °C can be related to the Hopkinson effect. The Hopkinson effect is manifested as a sharp magnetic permeability maximum at

temperatures slightly below the Curie temperature, T_c , [36][37]. The origin of such effect is commonly associated with a faster decrease of magnetic anisotropy constant with temperature as compared to the magnetization.

A comparison of the hysteresis loops measured at different T (see Figure 5a) shows that, indeed, higher magnetic permeability is observed at $T= 300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, as

Figure 5. Change in the hysteresis of studied samples upon heating (a) and $H_k(T)$ dependencies evaluated from hysteresis loops (c).

Figure 6. $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at 50 MHz (a) and 100 MHz (b) at room temperature before and after heating and at $T=300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

compared to the hysteresis loops measured at $T= 200\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $250\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (see Figure 5 a).

The evolution of average magnetic anisotropy field, H_k , upon heating is provided in Figure 5b. Such H_k –values were evaluated from the hysteresis loops, as previously described [38].

In order to separate the effect of heating from the effect of the internal stresses relaxation, the comparison of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies measured at room temperature before and after heating up to $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is provided in Figure 6.

A comparison of the $\Delta Z/Z(H)$ dependencies (see Figure 6 a,b) clearly shows some $\Delta Z/Z_{\max}$ improvement after heating to $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This increase in $\Delta Z/Z_{\max}$ must be related to the relaxation of internal stresses. However, the main contribution to the increase in $\Delta Z/Z_{\max}$ is related to the heating itself.

The observed experimental results on substantial temperature dependence of the GMI effect and magnetic properties of Fe-rich microwires can be useful for temperature monitoring. However, the effect of heating must be separated from the internal stresses relaxation upon heating.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The temperature dependence of the magnetic properties and the GMI effect of amorphous FeSiBC microwires have been thoroughly analyzed using both hysteresis loops and GMI measurements. A substantial change in hysteresis loops shape and GMI effect upon heating is observed. We observed a remarkable improvement of the GMI ratio and modification of hysteresis loops from rectangular to inclined upon heating of FeSiBC microwire. The observed experimental results are discussed considering relaxation of internal stresses upon heating, Hopkinson effect and modification of the thermal expansion coefficients upon heating.

The observed significant effect of temperature on the hysteresis loop shape and the GMI effect of FeSiBC microwires coated by insulating, flexible and biocompatible glass-coating opens up the possibility of using such Fe-rich microwires for temperature sensors and for temperature monitoring in composites with magnetic microwire inclusions.

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